

ISic1110

I.Sicily inscription 1110

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Cinisi

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]τα Σωτηρίδ

2. [α][---][εὐν]φίας χάριν

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo and Erdas 2019

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491443

EDR 136440

EDCS 39102267

PHI 140593

PHI 175608

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0289 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 14

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5544 and p.1249

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. Siciliae et adjacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata. Palermo. At cl.VII no.8

De Vido, S. 1991. appendice: fonti letterarie, epigrafiche, numismatiche, etc.. *ASNP*. 21: 929-994. At 972

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta. Pisa. At G9

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